

MANAGING POLLARDED TREES IN AGROFORESTRY

1. Pollard trees at the edge of the field (see webpage link at the end) 2. Pollard pruning at GAEC de la Bunouderie © Ver de Terre Production
3. Pollarding on a goat willow with sap collection preserved © Gilles Leblais
4. Pollard trees, true refuges for biodiversity (Little Owl (top left) ; Brown Long-eared Bat (top right) ; Stoat (bottom left) ; female European Green Woodpecker (bottom right)) © Gilles Leblais

THE WHAT AND WHY

Pollard tree management, also known as "trognes," is an ancient technique involving regular topping of trees at a specific height to stimulate the production of shoots. Pollard trees offer a consistent biomass production, exceeding that of an unpruned tree. These shoots can be used for various purposes: firewood, timber, fodder, basketry, bedding for livestock, wood chips, etc. The type of production can change over time, depending on the landowner's needs. Traditionally planted at the edges of fields, pollards can also be integrated into within-field agroforestry systems, with canopy shading controlled and reduced water competition due to periodic leaf surface reduction. This practice contributes to sustainable resource management, promoting autonomy and short supply chains.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

A pollard tree is typically created on a young tree with a trunk diameter between 5 and 20 cm. It can be an existing tree, a stump shoot, a natural seedling, a planted tree, or a cutting. For the first three years, cutting is repeated to form the "head," and successive healing makes the pollard grow progressively. Depending on agricultural constraints and livestock access needs, the canopy is usually cut to a height of 1.5 to 3 meters. Shoots are then harvested every 5 to 15 years, depending on the species and use, keeping the tree vigorous and supporting biodiversity. Maintenance pruning is done mainly in winter for timber production and in summer for fodder.

Keywords: Agroforestry, pollards, pruning, trees, biodiversity, sustainable resource

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ADVANTAGES

Pollard trees provide a wide range of ecosystem services. Their root systems intercept runoff, increase soil porosity, and enhance water infiltration, protecting the land from erosion and contributing to groundwater recharge. They also improve soil fertility, store carbon, and protect crops from wind and extreme temperatures.

Additionally, pollard trees create habitats for numerous beneficial organisms, including pollinating insects, birds of prey, and other natural predators of rodents. They act as ecological corridors, promoting the movement of species and improving cross-pollination. Pollard trees fulfill the same ecological roles as traditional agroforestry but with an added benefit: this pruning technique creates cavities in the trunk, offering a special ecological niche for biodiversity. For example, cavity-dwelling birds like the little owl, the white-fronted redstart, and the great spotted woodpecker use these cavities for nesting and protection. Similarly, bats, essential for maintaining agricultural ecosystem balance by controlling insect populations, use pollards as roosting and hibernating sites. Some wood-boring insects, such as beetles, rely on dead wood and cavities for development, helping to recycle organic matter by decomposing the wood.

In agroforestry, pollards maximize land use by combining tree production with crops or livestock, while minimizing light and water competition. Lastly, pollards, with their longevity and regenerative capacity, are a natural and cultural heritage that must be preserved.

This technique applies to most native broadleaf trees, but some species are more suited than others, such as willow, ash, black poplar, oak, plane, mulberry, hornbeam, field maple, linden, and chestnut.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **In the context of climate change, pollards provide a resilient solution in agroforestry due to their water retention and environmental stress adaptation.**
- **Economically, pollard cutting provides a renewable, local resource of wood and fodder, reducing external purchases and increasing farm autonomy.**
- **Pollard trees, true biodiversity refuges, offer varied habitats for many species through their cavities, hollows, and dead wood.**

Pollard tree in the Jabron Valley (Alpes de Haute-Provence) © M. Marguerie

<https://www.agroforesterie.fr/formation/la-trogne-larbre-paysan-aux-mille-usages/>

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.